

THE ELECTRODEPOSITION OF NICKEL ON IRON AND THE EFFECT OF COLLOIDS ON THE NATURE OF DEPOSIT.

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The action of different inorganic colloids, both of elements and salts, on the electrodeposition of nickel on iron has been found to have a very good effect in so far as they give hard lustrous deposits with minimum number of pits. Prussian blue sol comes next in order. The formation of pits has been discussed.

The action of inorganic colloids on the electrodeposition of nickel on copper has been investigated in this laboratory (Puri and Bhatia, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 71). It was seen that the colloids can be classified under two heads, *viz.*, those which have a beneficial effect and those which give dark, loose and spongy deposits. The present work was undertaken to study the effect of addition of colloids on the electrodeposition of nickel on iron. It is of a very great technical importance as the process has extensive applications in industry. For this purpose the final product should be non-rusting and capable of taking a high degree of polish. Further, the layer of nickel should not corrode easily. Various colloids were tried to achieve these ends and the results of our experiments are given in the present paper.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The bath solutions and apparatus employed were the same as those used by previous workers (*loc. cit.*). The electrodes were subjected to a preliminary cleansing treatment given below :

Iron Plate (Cathode).—The iron strip ($6'' \times 1'' \times 0.2''$) was taken and rubbed on a No. 7 grinding wheel in order to remove the rust stains and to obtain an even, uniform surface. It was then rubbed with sand paper No. 1 $\frac{1}{2}$ across the lines, and then with No. 0 until the plate was smooth to touch. It was finally rubbed on a felt bob.

The plate was then boiled in a concentrated solution of sodium hydroxide to remove grease and pickled in a 10.1% solution of sulphuric acid for one minute and washed with distilled water. It was dried in a cold blast of air.

Nickel Plate.—(*Vide* Puri and Juneja, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 581).

The bath was kept in a thermostat regulated at 25° and connected in series with a copper voltameter. A current of 0.30 amp. was passed.

Preparation of Colloids.

Silver Sol.—One type of silver sol was prepared by Bredig's electrical dispersion method and an olive-green solution was obtained. This solution after about a week's standing changed to a clear reddish brown liquid with some sediment at the bottom. The other type of silver sol was the same as that used by Puri and Bhatia (*loc. cit.*).

Red Gold Sol.—Gold chloride (1 g.) was dissolved in water and the solution neutralised by cautious addition of sodium carbonate and the volume made up to 100 c.c. to give a 1% solution. This solution (10 c.c.) was taken in a pyrex flask and made up to 100 c.c. 3 C.c. of 0.1% solution of tannin were added to this gradually and a ruby red gold sol was obtained immediately.

Blue Gold Sol.—This solution was obtained by reducing gold chloride with hydrazine hydrate prepared in the laboratory. The sol obtained thus was blue.

Sulphur Sol.—*Vide* Puri and Juneja (*loc. cit.*).

Prussian Blue Hydrosol—Puri and Bhatia (*loc. cit.*).

Silver Iodide (Positive) Sol.—To 40 c.c. of 0.05N-silver nitrate solution 11 c.c. of 0.1N-KI solution were added drop by drop while the flask was being shaken thoroughly and continuously. A concentrated sol of AgI, green yellow in colour, was obtained.

Silver Iodide (Negative) Sol.—To 220 c.c. of 0.05N-KI solution, 18 c.c. of 0.1N-AgNO₃ solution were added. The colour of the AgI sol was just the same as that of the AgI positive sol. Silver chloride and silver bromide sols were similarly prepared.

Effect of Colloids.

Silver Sol (Bredig's electrical dispersion method).—The amounts used were 4, 8, 12 and 16 c.c. of the solution. The deposit became firm with 4 c.c. and still more so with 16 c.c. of the colloid. However, it was not uniform near the bottom of the plate. The number of pits was reduced.

Silver Sol (Tannin method).—The amounts used was 4, 8, 12 and 16 c.c. 4 C.c. of colloidal solution contained 0.000864 g. of silver. The deposit was bright and lustrous in all cases and it could take on a high polish. With 4 and 8 c.c. the deposit was fairly hard but the addition of 12 and 16 c.c. of the colloid gave a uniformly thick and the hardest deposit. The

number of pits was successively reduced in all the cases. Unlike the sol obtained by Bredig's method, the pits had a conch-like appearance (Fig. A).

Red Gold Sol.—The deposit was bright and lustrous and could be given a high degree of polish. Also, it was hard, coherent and would not peel off easily. With 4 c.c. *i.e.* 0.000696 g. of gold large pits were obtained. They were, however, very few in number. Upto 12 c.c. the number of pits increased, after the addition of 16 c.c. the number of pits did not appreciably alter. In outline the pits resemble the conch (*cf.* Cymboliste, *Trans. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1936, 70, 16), but in structure they take after those obtained with the Prussian blue sol. They have a central high spot alternating with elliptical rings and a light annular ring between the two.

Blue Gold Sol.—The addition of this colloid caused an increase in the lustre in the order 16 c.c. (*i.e.* 0.00032 g. of gold) > 4 c.c. > 8 c.c. > 12 c.c. With 16 c.c. the deposit became very hard. There were a few 'trailing' globules in the deposit which was otherwise found to be fairly thick and and firm. With 12 and 16 c.c. there were no pits on the obverse side and very few on the reverse side.

Sulphur Sol.—The deposit was formed in patches. It had a burnt appearance and lacked lustre in all the cases. Except for the patches of the deposit the remaining areas were covered with clusters of coarsely crystalline nickel which could be easily detached from the plate. It was observed that the sol had been adsorbed and could not be washed away with carbon disulphide. With 16 c.c. (*i.e.* 0.000704 g. of sulphur) of the sol the deposit became loose and spongy and a portion of it fell into the bath. Fig. B shows the nickel crystals on the cathode, with adsorbed sulphur, highly magnified.

Prussian Blue Hydrosol—Lustre increased with increasing amounts of the colloid. The plate could take a good polish. It was uniformly hard except with 16 c.c. of the colloid when it became less firm. Small globules of nickel were, however, found scattered all over the surface with 4 c.c. *i.e.* 0.000264 g. of the colloid and 'pitting' occurred near the bottom. With 8 c.c. their number decreased. With increased amounts of the sol a few large pits could be discerned. The 'pits' were circular and very deep. Fig. C shows them to consist of a round dark spot surrounded by a lighter annular ring. The colloid was found embedded in the substance of the electro-plate. The colloid could not be easily washed off.

Silver Iodide Sol (Positive).—With 4 c.c. *i.e.* 0.01504 g. of AgI the plate became lustrous at places. It had a burnt look; scattered shiny black patches appeared with increased amounts of colloid. The deposit was loose

and crystals of nickel concentrated on the edges. Large areas were not plated at all.

Silver Iodide (Negative), Silver Chloride and Silver Bromide sols behaved in a like manner.

Pits during the Process of Formation.

While examining the effect of blue gold sol an insight was afforded into the mode of formation of pits. Fig. D shows two of these pits which are beginning to be formed. The furrows appear to be quite deep. The open end of the horizontal V is then closed forming a unit pit. The limbs then further sheet out in order to form the 'compound' pit (Fig. E). The wings, next, complete the outline of the 'compound' pit. Further developments now take place in the enclosed area which is gradually excavated until it takes the final shape of the depression or a pit.

It may be mentioned here that the effects produced in every case discussed above are from colloidal suspensions and not from the sols in the general sense of the word. As the bath is highly electrolytic in nature the presence of such a suspension is inevitable but it has been observed that this suspension takes days to settle and if stirring is constantly done it settles hardly at all. That the colloids have a marked effect on the amount and nature of deposit appears to be beyond any doubt.

D I S C U S S I O N.

Two types of colloids were tried namely the colloidal elements and salts in the colloidal state. The silver and gold sols were found to have a beneficial effect in so far as they gave hard and lustrous deposits. The number of pits also decreased. The Prussian blue hydrosol comes next in order of efficiency. It gives bright deposits which are capable of taking a high polish.

The halides of silver and elements like sulphur give results which are least satisfactory from the point of view of their utilization in industry.

It has been noticed that with blue gold sol the number of pits decreases with the increase in concentration of the colloid. It is very difficult to offer an explanation for the formation of pits. The explanation given by some workers that pits are formed under the seat of a bubble of hydrogen gas, which is evolved in the electrolysis, seems to be incorrect for two reasons :

(1) That the gas bubbles were not allowed to settle on the cathode and still the pits appeared.

(2) That where a few bubbles were allowed to remain, they were kept under observation and after the completion of the experiment pits were not necessarily underneath them.

Where a pit is found under the seat of a hydrogen bubble, it is probable that impurities in the cathode plate cause polarization, owing to local differences of potential, with the consequent formation of a pit and the evolution of hydrogen gas.

It appears, however, that the initial condition of a plate, as far as surface texture is concerned, does not affect the formation of a pit. Work is still in progress in this laboratory.

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